

Role of Communication Skills in Effective Management of Library and Information Centres

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Abstract

The present paper attempts to study the importance of communication skill in library professionals as interpersonal communication as a form of communication is one of the ways in the library service. Interpersonal communication is intended to invite or serve the members and the response their entire objection in a proper, effective and fun way. For positive feedback from customers as a result of sincerely and openly by official the librarian can acknowledge the best solutions for the members. Libraries have to meet with the many kinds of character and behavior. Having librarians and being able to apply interpersonal communication skills will give a positive impression to users. This paper describes types of management skills required in 21st century to improve the communication skills of librarians, so that they can easily go through its activities.

Key words: Communication, Skills, Development, Library, Information.

Introduction

Communication between audience and librarians can help users a great deal, especially those who are new to the library, by informing and educating them about collections, rules and policies, and procedures for borrowing books, and soon. Communication is mutual. There is a growing recognition that information and communication are integral in very fundamental ways. The development of Communication and Information/Library Studies has a long tradition of common interests and concepts.

Communication is not something that happens in an incoherent fashion. It is a transfer of a cluster of transferable functions of body and mind of one individual to another. Communication is said to possess the following characteristics:

- Intention of the communicator
- Nature of communication
- Emphasis on action, measurability of action
- Comparability of intention and measured action.

Communication process always requires at least three basic elements: the source, message and the destination. In fact, source is the point at which messages originate. It is also referred to as sender or invader of information. A source may be an individual speaking, writing, gesturing, or a communication organisation like newspaper, publishing house, television station, etc. Message may be in the form of written or printed text, sound or light waves in the air, influences in the electric current, or in the form of any other signal which is capable of being explained meaning fully. Destination is the intended target of the message, could be an individual or a group and the final link in the communication chain.

Objectives of The Study

- To study the need for management skills for librarian's.
- To describe the need for management skills for library professionals.

Importance of Communication Skills for Library Management

Attitude is the way a person accepts or denies something based on the way he or she judges a particular object that may or may not be appropriate for him/her. Attitude too can be interpreted tends to respond positively and negatively to a particular person, object or situation. In other words, a person can develop the attitude as a result of a feedback to the attitude object. While the behavior can be explained impulse that exists in humans, while the motivation that exists in humans is an attempt to meet the needs that must be met in humans.

Interpersonal communication also be comes interpersonal communication. Interpersonal communication is a person to person interaction between two or more persons in which the sender can deliver a message direct and receiver of the aircraft can receive and respond directly. Another opinion says interpersonal communication is the communication between people face-to-face, roommates allows that each participant to strike the reaction of others directly, verbally or nonverbal.

In improving the quality of service communication skills plays an important part. One of the criteria required libraries are library users who have good communication skills and mature personality to build positive relationships with others. While with regard to communication made by libraries, libraries are considered to be stiff, closed and tend to engage in their own activities. It is coherent if the librarian is busy with their own activities being seen, it is because librarians tend to get fastened in endless technical activities.

The work burden and work environment sometimes make it more stressful and more temperate. This gives a negative impression on the image of libraries and a library. The negative image of librarians is often fixed in the minds of the public and can damage the procedures that were built. For those measures that can be offered to build a positive image of librarians we need to.

The ability to communicate in this regard interpersonal communication is very important for libraries as the librarian jobs that have direct contact with the user. Librarian skills in performing effective interpersonal communication will determine the success of librarians in their work. The different ways of communicating libraries can be determined by a number of things, namely attitude and behavior. In addition, the librarian's quality is also influenced by various factors, namely the educational back ground that will determine the skills, personality, and ability to communicate. Librarians must have the mutual skills of effective communication in the form of:

- *Disclosure*: Librarian at the service of the user must be open and trustworthy. Of ten we find libraries delighted by the user. In such situations among communicators (librarians and users) will create the acceptance of feelings and thoughts, and each party is responsible for what it light up.
- *Supportive Behavior*: Libraries also need to show an interesting attitude that supports user to communicate with him. Often we find that in the library, the user sometimes feels very annoying to stay in the library because they are steadily being supervised by the librarian. In addition, we often face the writings in the form of band is tributed in the library. An example of this is there striction confirmed at the entrance of the library, such as wearing a jacket and bags forbidden, out lawed to bring food and many things. Such are striction is highly not communicative and produces a negative image of libraries and libraries. Actually, a prohibition that is in the library can be communicated in a language that is positive and impressed as, Thank you for not bringing food in the library, Thank you for not smoking in the library.
- *Positive Behavior*: Libraries should put the user as an important person to be treated properly. The thing that can do is to address the user with words that kind of kindness with a sweet smile. This makes the user feel valued and instead they will also enjoy the professional libraries as

respectable.

- *Empathy*: The librarian must be able to feel what is seen by the user without defeated their identity. An example is when a user who is hard to use a diary used as a reference for university assignments. While the magazine is very difficult to obtain, but the assignment has to be collected in the near future. To do this, the librarian has to live in what is experienced by the user. Things to do are to help users quickly find the magazine in question and try to provide information.
- *Attitude*: Along with the development of technology and current information, it is time for librarians to adapt by developing capability in both hard skills related to technical, social skills and skills in information technology. It's time for the existence itself that librarian is intelligent, managing his work well and being able to communicate well with users.
- *Cohesion*: Librarian in this case must be able to show an interest in user problems. Things can be done by showing the librarian uneasiness and a sense of its importance to express non-verbal messages, such as giving a sincere smile, a friendly gaze and body-friendly body language. If a librarian is able to do that, the user will be more excited to bring their complaints and ask the librarian relevant information that he needs when visiting the library. So users have that unease and who are uncertain to ask the librarian will be less willing to ask the librarian.
- *Interaction Management*: The process of communication that takes place between librarians and users sometimes takes inequality. For that, librarians must be able to effectively manage the process of continuous communication between the librarian and the user. Libraries can create an intimate atmosphere that makes the communication between them flexible. If the communication goes well then it is certain that the users are able to be clearly expressed what he needs, and the librarian was well understood.
- *Expressive behavior*: In serving the librarian, the attitude he was interested into the subject of the ongoing discussions should be demonstrated. This interest rate must be demonstrated by the attitude of the body and concerned style of communication. Librarians also pay attention to what was said by the user. Forms can be accomplished venues relate to facts giving feedback or right and positive feedback from user.

Management Skills Needed for Library Professionals

In the 21st century information technology age the concept of library is totally changed. A library professional that has management skills can easily grow in providing information and services. The following are the skills that are required in all library professional to perform their duties.

Table 1: Management skills required for library professionals

Sl.	Types of Skills	Features
1.	Technical skills	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Word Processing Skills • Spreadsheets Skills • Database Skills • Electronic Presentation Skills • Web Navigation Skills • Web Site Design Skills • E-Mail Management Skills • Digital Cameras • Computer Network Knowledge Applicable to your School System • File Management & Windows Explorer Skills
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Downloading Software From the Web (Knowledge including eBooks) • Installing Computer Software onto a Computer System • WebCT or Blackboard Teaching Skills

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Videoconferencing skills • Computer-Related Storage Devices (Knowledge:disks, CDs, USB drives, zip disks, DVDs) • Scanner Knowledge • Knowledge of PDAs • Deep Web Knowledge • Educational Copyright Knowledge • Computer Security Knowledge
2.	Performanceskills	The librarian is a technology application leader who works with other members of the information management team to design and evaluate systems for information access that meet user needs. The librarian provides instruction and support so that end users can make excellent use of the information resources available to them. Librarians should be capable of working in the hybrid world of print and electronic media and providing the best mix of information resources in the most applicable formats for the environment.
3.	Communicationskills	Library managers are first and foremost communicators. Although there is no such thing as a 'typical day', for these managers most days "usually involve meetings, either to discuss projects, ideas, or challenges, or to pass on information, instruction, or training".
4.	Leadership skills	Library leaders must be able to work with all kinds of people and reflect a "helpful and outgoing personality." This ability to consider the thoughts and inputs of others has a calming effect that allows them to set a positive direction and balance compassion and firmness. A good sense of humor is also a must.
5.	Time management skills	Time management is most prominent in day to day life. They manage their time perfectly so they can achieve success in their career. In the library, professionals can save the users' time such as a timely reply for their queries, providing a current awareness service, reprography service, reference service and procurement of books and resources on time and after procurement completes the book process as early as possible and delivers the book to the users. To achieve the vision and mission of the library time management is stress-free. Technology guide libraries for managing time such as RFID, Barcode, QR code, Kiosks, Book lifts, etc.
6.	Team building skills	An ability to establish working relations with others, defining, sharing and delegating responsibilities within a group and encouraging people to work effectively in groups. Ability to cooperate with others and make a variety of contributions like ideas, organisation in a joint venture.
7.	Teaching skills	Librarians can help find important information for patrons on books or complex subjects. Librarians have basic research skills and know how to search for accurate, day-to-day information from both online and offline sources, because libraries value providing excellent information and educating the community.
8.	Presentationskills	Accurate documentation helps a librarian organize information and maintain accurate library records. Generally, a library uses software to create documentation, including applications for library cards, library fine information, patron information, event information or the library catalog. Librarians understand how to use documentation software

		to create store and shared documents and maintain complete
		records.

Conclusion

Librarian is the main profession in the library service all over the world. Presently, the social vision of the librarian's profession remains negative. Librarians considered old-fashioned, unfriendly, impressed and rarely communicated with the user. Communicative skills are a very important factor for the librarian's activity with the user, so librarian must have an effective communication skill. The communication skills are included: openness, positive behavior, supporting behavior, empathy, equality, self-assured attitude, togetherness, interaction management and expressive behavior. With effective communication skills owned by the librarian must be able to build a positive self image of librarian's as well as improve the quality of library services.

However, it is also important that library users play a part in ensuring that libraries deliver the service that is needed. Librarians accepted the opportunity to find out what readers want and to better understand how to deliver relevant and timely services. It is only by working together and building on each other's knowledge and experience that we can improve the services.

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